

Women's role in agricultural resilience of Indigenous communities

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September 23, 2024

“In the age of information, things are buzzing all over the Earth. Humans have abundant information to keep them entertained all day, and even in The Bird Village, there is excitement in the air.”

—In “Titles of Nobility”; *Wild Wise Weird* (2024)

[SCIENCE COMMUNICATION]

Women play a crucial role in addressing agricultural challenges, particularly in conservation and the adoption of innovative farming practices. Women's deep connection to the land and ecosystems enables them to navigate the socioeconomic impacts of climate change effectively. By utilizing traditional networks to share planting materials and strategies, women can encourage community-wide responses, highlighting their adaptability and leadership during difficult times [1].

Sidchogan-Batani [2] emphasizes the resilience and adaptability of Kankanaey women in the Philippines's indigenous communities, particularly their crucial role in preserving agricultural heritage amidst shifting environmental conditions. Their integration of traditional practices, such as *alluyon* (mutual labor exchange), with modern farming

technologies showcases the value of Indigenous knowledge in addressing climate change. By leading these efforts, Kankanaey women not only foster community collaboration but also enhance the collective capacity for implementing effective climate adaptation strategies.

From the perspective of granular interaction thinking [3], the knowledge possessed by women can be considered informational capital, valuable alongside physical and financial assets. Grounded in generations of experience with local ecosystems, biodiversity, and seasonal shifts, this knowledge is crucial for developing climate-resilient strategies. It forms part of a broader network of ecological, cultural, and agricultural practices. This dynamic framework, which blends traditional practices with modern scientific approaches, supports the sustainable management of forests, water, and soil.

Illustration. Working women. Source. <https://www.resilience.org/stories/2023-03-08/women-in-agriculture/>

Kankanaey women exemplify the integration of traditional ecological knowledge with scientific approaches, particularly in disaster risk reduction. Their expertise in seed

varieties and agricultural methods makes them key contributors to community resilience. The intergenerational transmission of indigenous knowledge plays a critical role in preserving crop diversity and fostering adaptive strategies rooted in cultural heritage. By blending traditional and modern practices, Kankanaey women enable more flexible responses to climate hazards, strengthening overall community resilience [2].

However, the growing shift toward cash crop farming introduces new challenges, often creating tensions between traditional practices and evolving social dynamics. External development projects that do not align with local needs risk disrupting the balance between indigenous agricultural systems and the adoption of new technologies. To ensure successful interventions, development efforts need to respect the cultural and ecological knowledge that sustains indigenous practices [4].

In summary, the case of Kankanaey communities suggests that effective support for Indigenous communities requires development interventions that align with their evolving needs and empower women as leaders. By integrating traditional and scientific knowledge systems, we can enhance resilience and foster sustainable climate adaptation strategies that respect local cultures and environments. This interdisciplinary approach offers a better understanding of how indigenous knowledge systems enable communities to navigate the challenges posed by climate change.

References

[1] Unay-Gailhard I, Bojnec S. (2021). Gender and the environmental concerns of young farmers: Do young women farmers make a difference on family farms? *Journal of Rural Studies*, **88**, 71-82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.09.027>

[2] Sidchogan-Batani R. (2018). Engaging women's knowledge and practices in negotiating climate hazards: The integrative roles of Kankanaey women. *Urban Anthropology and Studies of Cultural Systems and World Economic Development*, **47**(1/2), 39-75. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/45172887>

[3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better economics for the Earth: A lesson from quantum and information theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>

[4] Imoro, ZA., et al. (2021). Harnessing indigenous technologies for sustainable management of land, water, and food resources amidst climate change. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5, 691603. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/sustainable-food-systems/articles/10.3389/fsufs.2021.691603/full>

[5] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

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